

Employing SiO₂ nano-particles in conformal and in-cup structures of 8500 K white LEDs

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ABSTRACT

SiO₂ nano-particles have been examined in a distant phosphor structure for the elevated luminous quality and better consistency of white light-emitting diodes with angular-dependent associated color temperature (CCT). The luminous scattering ability could be increased by applying SiO₂ nano-particles contain silicone to the outside of the phosphorus coating. In specific, the strength of blue light at wide angles is increased and differences in CCT can be minimized. In addition, owing to the sufficient refractive indices of silicone-containing SiO₂ nanoparticles between the air and phosphorus layers, the luminous flux was improved. This new configuration decreases angular-dependent CCT deviations in the range of -70° to 70° from 1000 to 420 K. In comparison, at a 120 mA driving current, the rise of lumen flux increased by 2.25% relative to an usual distant phosphor structure without SiO₂ nano-particles. As a result, in a distant phosphor structure, the SiO₂ nano-particles could not only enhance the uniformity of illumination but also enhance the output of light.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Light emitting diodes (LEDs) are utilized commonly such as replacements for frequently utilized incandescent bulbs and fluorescent lamps which are ineffective or include mercury [1]. Phosphors are normally added to blue light from LED chips that have down-conversion in order to recognize white light. Relied on the downshift of blue InGaN LEDs by Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Ce (YAG:Ce)-based yellow phosphors, white LEDs presently produce a “cold” white light with a poor color rendering index (CRI) and superior correlated color temperature (CCT). Phosphors have been pushed beyond the normal YAG: Ce. The demand to substitute incandescent lamps producing “warm” white color with a novel illumination supply with superior CRI and poor CCT has pushed phosphors outside the usual YAG: Ce. Mixing red emitted phosphors with yellow phosphors will enhance color intensity but capacity of the energy of LEDs will be remarkably reduced [2]. After that, among light output and white LED power efficiency there will be an exchange. Lately, as potential candidates for light emissions, semiconductor nanocrystals or quantum dots (QDs) have been introduced to adjust the emission spectrum of standard white LEDs that have the decreased reduction of capacity quality [3]. QDs are effective visible light emissions that provide extremely narrow emission spectrums with precisely adjustable wavelengths of emission. Thus, highly effective white LEDs which have superior CRI are predicted. However, QDs require a consistent combination of a silicone polymer in the

packing procedure of white LEDs and above ligands of QDs could potentially impede the polymerizing or decrease the mechanical stability of packing stuffs [4]. In addition, the appropriation with silicone polymers with polarization, which is liked better in LED manufacturing, is reduced by the long chain outside-covering ligands with the hydrophobicity. Ziegler et al. recommended silica-encapsulated QDs to resolve these difficulties and have a high CRI for increased LED emission spectrums. Nanocomposites which have the base of inorganic nanocrystals have been of great attentiveness in previous decades as the ability of them to control their physical and chemical features for diverse implementations like light-emitting diodes (LEDs), catalysts, creating biological images [5]-[9]. The most thoroughly studied of these are silica-based nanocomposites with quantum dots (QDs). Though many routes have been attempted to nanocomposites which have the base of silica with precisely scattered QDs, the process including a interchange stage of ligand as for the semiconductor nanocrystal hydrophilic outside-covering and following expansion using the Stober method of silica shell layer is one of the more common routes [10], [11]. Additionally, to synthesize SiO₂-nanocrystal composite particles, an opposite micelle technique was also commonly adopted [12]-[15]. In order to induce the production of reverse micelles, surfactants have been used and silica precursors (e.g. tetraethylorthosilicate, TEOS) are hydrolyzed/condensed at the interface of water and oil. With this method, a smug silica outside-covering was acquired because of the great monodispersity. Koole et al. recently indicated that hydrolyzed TEOS could substitute the water repellent ligands of the QD facade where silica development occurs. Although the amount of nanocrystals embedded in each nanocomposite particle is typically restricted, SiO₂ nanohybrids with numerous nanocrystals at great concentrations are used in the synthesis of greatly luminescent phosphors for many implementations [16].

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1. MC-WLEDs simulation

An illustration of the structure of WLEDs is given in Figure 1. Samples with remote phosphorous formations are produced in the plastic lead-frame box in the following stages: (1) a square blue LED chips has the size of 24 mils and a greatest emission wavelength of 450 nm are mounted. The radiant flux of the pure blue LED chips of a moving current of 120 mA was 95 mW, (2) By dispensing, the translucent silicone is loaded in the lead frame and cured for 1 h at 150°C, (3) The phosphorus dusts are amalgamated with a silicone adhesive and a solvent has the base of alkyl in order to create phosphorus termination slurry. As previously shown, the pulsation spray covering with the time management could boost the phosphorous slurry quality [17], [18].

The phosphorous Y₃Al₅O₁₂ (YAG) is used with a particle size of around 12 μm in this experiment. The phosphorous slurry is then sprayed on the translucent silicone surface to form the usual distant phosphorous, Figure 1(a). The manufacture of nanoparticles of SiO₂ with distant phosphorous configuration varies only in the final stage from the usual distant phosphorous configuration, Figure 1(b). SiO₂ nano-particles are combined and sprayed on the surface of the phosphorous substrate with an alkyl-based solvent and a silicone adhesive, with a 5% concentration of SiO₂ nano-particles. The LED is chosen for contrast at a moving current of 120 mA which has the similar color temperature and color intensity coordinates. So as to examine the investigational consequence of SiO₂ nano-particles in the silicone sealant, the cross-sectional scanning electron microscopic (SEM) illustration is also used. It demonstrates the size of SiO₂ nano-particles at approximately 300 nm, Figure 1(c). An energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) was examined for the portion of SiO₂ nano-particles with silicone encapsulant, as shown in Figure 1(d). In the silicone encapsulant, we can check the presence of Si and O components.

Figure 1. These figures are, (a) Picture of WLEDs form, (b) The simulated WLEDs model, (c) Conformal phosphor structure, (d) In-cup phosphor structure

2.2. Scattering computation

The Mie theoretical [19]-[22] findings and the ray-tracing outcomes are farther debated as a possibility to figure out if the Mie theory could be updated by an uncomplicated approach to provide an extra detailed explanation of the optic characteristics of phosphorus. It is as Mie theory is commonly applied in a lot of mercantile optic softwares such as LightTools, Tracepro, and ASAP, which normally considers phosphor scattering to be Mie scattering to recognize the optic simulation of the packaging of white LED. Altered Mie optic constant calculations can give fair optical simulation assistance and help the software in a superior way in the LED packaging design. The scattering coefficient $\mu_{sca}(\lambda)$, anisotropy factor $g(\lambda)$, and declined scattering coefficient $\delta_{sca}(\lambda)$ could be calculated by the calcutions (1), (2), and (3) according to the Mie-scattering theory:

$$\mu_{sca}(\lambda) = \int N(r)C_{sca}(\lambda, r)dr \tag{1}$$

$$g(\lambda) = 2\pi \int_{-1}^1 p(\theta, \lambda, r) f(r) \cos \theta d \cos \theta dr \tag{2}$$

$$\delta_{sca} = \mu_{sca}(1 - g) \tag{3}$$

Where $N(r)$ shows diffusion particle distribution density (mm^3), C_{sca} is the diffusion cross-section (mm^2), $p(\theta, \lambda, r)$ is the phase function, λ is the luminous wavelength (nm), r is the diffusion particle radius (μm), θ is the scattering angle ($^{\circ}C$), and $f(r)$ is the phosphorous layer diffuser distribution function, which can be computed as shown below [23], [24]:

$$f(r) = f_{dif}(r) + f_{phos}(r) \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} N(r) &= N_{dif}(r) + N_{phos}(r) \\ &= K_N \cdot [f_{dif}(r) + f_{phos}(r)] \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The diffusive particle density $N_{dif}(r)$ and the phosphor particle density $N(r)$ consisting of $N_{phos}(r)$. $f_{dif}(r)$ and $f_{phos}(r)$ are the function data of the diffuser and the dimension dispensation of phosphor particle. K_N is the diffuser unit number for a single diffuser concentration and can be determined as below [25], [26]:

$$c = K_N \int M(r)dr \tag{6}$$

Where $M(r)$ is the diffusive unit's mass distribution, proposed by the equation [27]:

$$M(r) = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 [\rho_{dif} f_{dif}(r) + \rho_{phos} f_{phos}(r)] \tag{7}$$

$\rho_{dif}(r)$ and $\rho_{phos}(r)$ are the density of diffuser and phosphor crystal. According to Mie theory, C_{sca} could be acquired by the calculation below [28]:

$$C_{sca} = \frac{2\pi}{k^2} \sum_0^{\infty} (2n - 1)(|a_n|^2 + |b_n|^2) \tag{8}$$

Where $k=2\pi/\lambda$, and a_n and b_n are computed as follows:

$$a_n(x, m) = \frac{\psi'_n(mx)\psi_n(x) - m\psi_n(mx)\psi'_n(x)}{\psi'_n(mx)\xi_n(x) - m\psi_n(mx)\xi'_n(x)} \tag{9}$$

$$b_n(x, m) = \frac{m\psi'_n(mx)\psi_n(x) - \psi_n(mx)\psi'_n(x)}{m\psi'_n(mx)\xi_n(x) - \psi_n(mx)\xi'_n(x)} \tag{10}$$

Where $x=k.r$, m is the refractive index, and $\psi_n(x)$ and $\xi_n(x)$ are the Riccati-Bessel function.

Therefore, the correlative refractive indices of diffusor (m_{dif}) and phosphor (m_{phos}) in silicone could be computed as $m_{dif} = n_{dif} / n_{sil}$ and $m_{phos} = n_{phos} / n_{sil}$. After that, the phase function could be shown as follows:

$$p(\theta, \lambda, r) = \frac{4\pi\beta(\theta, \lambda, r)}{k^2 C_{sca}(\lambda, r)} \quad (11)$$

Where $\beta(\theta, \lambda, r)$, $S_1(\theta)$ and $S_2(\theta)$ are the angular scatter amplitudes computed by the expressions below [29]:

$$\beta(\theta, \lambda, r) = \frac{1}{2} [|S_1(\theta)|^2 + |S_2(\theta)|^2] \quad (12)$$

$$S_1 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2n+1}{n(n+1)} \begin{bmatrix} a_n(x, m)\pi_n(\cos\theta) \\ +b_n(x, m)\tau_n(\cos\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$S_2 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2n+1}{n(n+1)} \begin{bmatrix} a_n(x, m)\tau_n(\cos\theta) \\ +b_n(x, m)\pi_n(\cos\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Even though the optical characteristics of the YAG: Ce crystal have been thoroughly analyzed, due to the various amounts of Ce doping, crystal growth approaches, and measuring instruments, the α differs in a wide range. The α variation is usually in the blue light spectrum of 3-8mm⁻¹. However, for optical YAG:Ce ceramics, composed of little crystal grains, the absorptivity of light is notably increased and the α may be greater than 15 mm⁻¹. It is owing to the numerous reflections inside the grain, which enhance the whole luminous absorptivity. Provided that the phosphorus studied is the powder composed of crystals and may therefore have great α , this analysis sets alpha ranged from 8 to 20 mm⁻¹ for the blue light to study the variants of C_{sca} (453). The estimated results of C_{sca} (453) are shown in Figure 2. According to (1), μ_{sca} is measured and shown in Figure 3. It can be shown in Figure 2 that one amplitude greater than the cross segment of absorption is the scattering cross segment, which means that the phosphorus has a powerful scatter impact and hence overcomes in great blue light absorptivity. With the rise of phosphorus concentration, the absorptivity and scatter coefficients are improved linearly in Figure 3, suggesting that changing the concentration of phosphorus is a direct response to white LED color control.

Figure 2. Scattering coefficients of SiO₂ particles

Figure 3. The phase function of SiO₂ particles

In the optic configuration of the measuring basis, light of blue or the light of yellow is generated from the above outside covering of the chip with a Lambertian pattern of radiation. The material for the lenses is Schott's BK7. The inside surfaces of the two merging spheres are covered with a diffuse white substance having optic characteristics of 11.1% absorptivity and 89.9% dispersion. The phosphor slide's help glass is also BK7 glass. In order to gather the emitted and reflected light, the surfaces inside the merging spheres are used as the receivers. For the ray tracing of the optical model, the Monte Carlo approach is applied. Phosphor is thought to be a material for dispersing Mie. Because the ray tracing is unable to measure the dispersion paths of the illumination in the phosphorus directly, the Henyey-Greenstein function is utilized as estimation for the angular dispersion generation, see Figure 3. We initially introduced the Mie theoretical results without any enhancement in the optic configuration. Nevertheless, the ray-tracing consequences

indicated that the transmission was slightly greater than that of the calculation overcomes and the absorptivity of the light of blue was lower than that of the calculation overcomes. These variations bring on three explanations. As compared with the real values, these are the lower μ_{abs} , lower μ_{sca} , and higher $g(\lambda)$. Therefore in the following simulations, three methodologies were introduced to achieve more accurate optical constants. The technique retained one of three constants unchanged in series and modified the other two constants to estimate the outcome of the experiment at the same time.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Generally, the consistency that depending on the angle of CCT could be described as the maximal CCT minus the minimal CCT. Diverse densities of SiO₂ nano-particles with a coating by silicone above the distant phosphorous formation are manufactured to advance the CCT aberration, Figure 4. This is evident that the littlest CCT aberrations and maximum density of SiO₂ nano-particles are seen at 10 mg cm⁻², which could achieve a 58% increase relative with the standard configuration of distant phosphorus. The inset illustration of Figure 4 illustrates the distant-field views of distant phosphor structures for normal and SiO₂ nano-particles. With the scattered function that SiO₂ nano-particles have, the light of blue and yellow can be evenly scattered. The CCT deviations will however be influenced by more SiO₂ nano-particles than 10 mg cm², but the quality is much higher than the conventional distant phosphorus configuration. The findings showed that the 10 mg cm² SiO₂ nano-particles' distant phosphorous configuration was not only able to boost the homogeneity of CCT that dependent on the angle, but also to enhance the flux of lamination.

Figure 4. CCT deviations of SiO₂ particles with different diameters, (a) Conformal structure, (b) In-cup geometry

The angular-dependent CCT of the distant phosphor structures of the normal and SiO₂ nano-particles is calculated and the SiO₂ layer weight is 10 mg cm⁻². Obviously, the angular-dependent CCT variance of the distant phosphorus structures of conventional and SiO₂ nano-particles has been increased from 1000 to 420 K in the scope of 700 to 700. The traditional distant phosphorus configuration has a lower angular CCT variance owing to the light of blue being limited and mirrored in the phosphor cover at a wide angle. Therefore, wide-angle extraction of blue light is minimized, leading to inefficient color blending of the light of blue and yellow. SiO₂ nanoparticles have a finer silicone angular-dependent CCT distribution on the phosphorous layer surface, as SiO₂ nano-particles may have an effective dispersion possibility to enhance the scale of the light of yellow to the light of blue at wide angles. Extra detailed examinations and a clarification would be presented at the following section. Figure 3 indicates the remote phosphor structures with the flux of lamination which is depending on the current of the traditional and SiO₂ nanoparticles have a mass of 10 mg cm⁻². The CCT of 5010 and 5097 K at a driving current of 120 mA for both distant phosphorous structures as manufactured are almost the same. It is also evident that, at a motion stream of 120 mA, the luminous flux of the SiO₂ nano-particle configuration rises by 2.25%. The variation in refractive indices among interfaces could be minimized with SiO₂ nanoparticles layer, and the extraction of light can be improved. Since the SiO₂ nanoparticles refractive index has silicone is approximately 1.5 and the SiO₂ nanoparticles refractive index has silicone is around 1.8, the SiO₂ nanoparticles contain silicone can have a gradient refractive indices between the layers of phosphorus and air. So as to explain the role of the scattered influence of the differences of the CCT and the flux of lamination, the CCTs which has the dependent on angle of LED packs including distinct quantities of SiO₂ nanoparticles were examined and demonstrated in Figure 4. As the instruments were doped with SiO₂ nanoparticles, the consistency of the CCTs which has the dependent on angle was enhanced dramatically. This observation reveals that the growth of the dopant's SiO₂

nanoparticle concentration created a greater scattering impact. Generally, the CCTs consistency has the definition of the maximal CCT minus the minimal CCT. Left out doping with SiO₂ nanoparticles, the correlation CCT was put at a great level (about 5319 K) and a greater CCT indicated a greater the light of blue extracted, which lead to an over CCT variance. The CCT differential found at 0° and 70° was effectively removed when the instruments were doped with SiO₂ nanoparticles. There was a clear impact of SiO₂ doping on phosphorus and silicone on the display of the packed equipment. However the optical features of SiO₂-doped films remain uncertain. In order to classify this combination of SiO₂-phosphor-silicone for further analysis, a sequence of thin-film experimentations were carried out, inclusive of transmitted absorption and haziness. At a wavelength of 460 nm compared to the normal dispensing configuration, the imbibition percentage in SiO₂ nanoparticle distributing configuration has been observed to rise from approximately 32% to almost 42%. This improvement resulted in the output of a greater portion of yellow light in the doped samplings of SiO₂, resulting in increasing the lighting performance. About this analysis, the effective index would change with the different SiO₂ nanoparticle concentrations after doping the SiO₂ nanoparticle in the phosphorus sheet. In comparison, the silicone, phosphorus and SiO₂ nanoparticle refractive indices (RI) are 1.4, 1.8 and 2.23. The RI of the SiO₂ nanoparticle phosphorous layer is then determined using the following equation [30]:

$$RI = V_1RI_1 + V_2RI_2 + V_3RI_3 \quad (15)$$

Where V_1 , V_2 and V_3 are the concentrations of the materials, the weight ratio of the materials is measured. The combining ratio of the SiO₂ nanoparticles to the phosphorus substrate in the dispensing structure was 1 wt% and 3 wt% for the SiO₂ nanoparticle dispensing structure. Therefore the phosphor layer RIs is 1.428 and 1.445 in each layer. A TFCalc32 simulation was used to address the influence of the various refractive index layers. The light extraction for the SiO₂ nanoparticle dispensing structure is about the same relative to the traditional dispensing structure because of the almost equal refractive index. Therefore the improvement of SiO₂ nanoparticle dispensing structure lumen flux could be credited solely to the SiO₂ nanoparticle's dispersing impact. In order to numerical assess the scattered impact on the SiO₂ nanoparticles; a Mie-scatter reproduction was presented to investigate the scattered influences of the distinct SiO₂ impurity concentrations. There were no phosphors in our model and only SiO₂ nanoparticles in the medium were present to decrease the model's complexity. At a wavelength of 460 nm, the RI of the SiO₂ nanoparticle contain silicone was 2.23. The SiO₂ particle size was about 300 nm and the impurity content was roughly 1% and 3% for SiO₂ nanoparticles. As the wavelength was greater than 500 nm, the haze amplitude of the virtual system structure with a lower SiO₂ dopant content presented nearly 100% before hitting 500 nm and dropped steadily. The scattering effect of SiO₂ refers to our experimental results, according to the simulated results. The haze amplitude for doping with a higher SiO₂ material was about the same as for wavelengths ranging from 300 to 700 nm, see Figure 5.

Figure 5. Luminous fluxes of SiO₂ particles with different diameters, (a) Conformal structure, (b) In-cup geometry

The full-field finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) simulation is used to show the effect with the CCT consistency and luminous production with distinct SiO₂ nano-particle dimensions to examine the scattered strength which dependent on angle of various SiO₂ nano-particle dimensions for the light of blue and yellow. The refractive indices of SiO₂ nano-particles contain silicone is around 1.5 under the simulated

conditions, and the SiO₂ nano-particles' concentration is 5%. The SiO₂ nano-particles of 400 nm has been noted to have a higher scattered strength which dependent on angle than other dimensions in both incident lights of blue (450 nm) and yellow (560 nm), Figure 6. While the better scattering effect may result in great consistency of the CCT, the transmission of the light of blue and yellow in the usual way is important to consider. As the film develops thicker from our calculation of refined SiO₂/silicone film, we could view a stable increasing pattern of absorption. This absorption will make up for 5%-15% of light and should be greater as the nano-particle size becomes larger in the 300 nm SiO₂ particle example. Therefore in order to determine this condition, extensive absorption details of various nano-particle sizes are required, but it is sure that for dispersion purposes, the nano-particle size can not be increased indefinitely, see Figure 7.

Figure 6. The reduced scattering coefficient of SiO₂ particles at different sizes and wavelength

Figure 7. The scattering cross section of SiO₂ particles at different sizes and wavelength

The correlated strength which dependent on angle of the light of blue and yellow, is determined in order to examine how the scatter of nanoparticles determines the radiation of the in-cup phosphor form. The divergence angle of the light of blue is wider than that of the standard one in SiO₂ nano-particles with a remote phosphorous structure and blue light is diminished in the usual way. These phenomena suggest that the dispersion influence of SiO₂ nano-particles greatly affects the optic direction of the light of blue, which is leading to the increasing of CCT aberration; alternatively, the distribution of the yellow light of standard phosphorous structures and the distribution of SiO₂ nano-particles is approximately the same. This can be understood from the wavelength dependency of the haze ratio: the haziness of the 10 mg cm⁻² sampling for yellow-colored photons (about 600 nm) is roughly 30% and 35% for blue-colored photons (about 450 nm). The larger the hazy scale, the higher the photon dispersion is. Correspondingly, blue photons are much more dispersed than yellow photons, which for SiO₂ samples on CCT may be helpful for color blending and cause less variance. This notion shows that the diffuse portion at wavelengths of yellow-colored light (600 nm) is a half of blue light and the haze calculation in Figure 5 also confirms this. These results indicate that in the distant phosphorus configuration, the CCT aberration is predominantly correlated with the divergence angle of the light of blue. In addition, the relative strength of blue light with distinct SiO₂ nano-particle weights at 700 was calculated as weight-dependent. Because of the maximum strength of the light of blue at broad angles, the SiO₂ nano-particle of 10 mg cm⁻² is considered to have an optimized state.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In brief, we have incorporated nanocomposites with the base of SiO₂ accomodating CdSe-ZnS quantum dots at great concentrations through spray-diffusion of QDs and farther encapsulating by hydrolysis and condensation of TEOS. By the application of APS after spray-diffusion of QDs, the marked reduction in the strength of emissivity of nanocomposites after TEOS/ammonia insert to the SiO₂ layers was suppressed. Moreover, before spray processing, it was demonstrated the amount of QDs compounded into the nanocomposites was regulated by the insert of APS. In order to measure the effects of QD-SiO₂ nanocomposites on the radiation spectrum of white LEDs, we have created a white-emitting LED with QD-SiO₂ nanocomposites with a great load of QDs. The luminous performance of the QD-SiO₂ nanocomposite white LED was equivalent to that of the blue LED with the load of YAG:Ce and showed a great CRI and a little fall in lamination performance.

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